

JOB STRESS AND STRESS MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AMONG LECTURERS IN DELTA STATE UNIVERSITY, ABRAKA

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Abstract

This study assessed job stress and management strategies among lecturers. Three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study focused on lecturers of Delta State University, Abraka. The research explored the causes, symptoms and management strategies of job stress among lecturers. Stress can be seen as a condition of mental pressure for some individuals facing problems from social and environmental well-being. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Comprehensive data of the lecturers of three (3) faculties selected for the study. The sample consist of 354 lecturers from faculty of education, Sciences and Social Sciences. A questionnaire containing 87 items was the instrument for data collection. The study was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of causes, symptoms and coping strategies of job stress were included that the lecturers experience a variety of stressors leading to variety of symptoms. Lecturers use different coping strategies to deal with stress. Base on the findings the following recommendations are made; Management should address the common stressors that lecturers face, Management should provide lecturers with support to help them cope with stress, Lecturers should develop healthy coping strategies. In contribution to knowledge, the study has identifying causes, symptoms and coping strategies to job stress.

Keywords: Causes of Stress, Symptoms of Stress, Management Strategies of Job Stress.

Introduction

There is no doubt that academic work environment is passing through a tremendous change, as a result of the effort put in for promotion by academic staff. Obidiegwu (2020) posited that the landscape of the higher education is continuously changing due to the changes impose by the environment. These changes have introduced more work load on the workers as a result heading to the increases of the stress in the environment. Obidiegwu (2020) sees job stress as a meaningful issue affecting employees of the 21st century in different work – places.

Despite the stress in the academic environment, it is a fact that teaching is perceived as the ancient and noblest of all professions. Teaching is very important in the realization of educational aims and objectives. Akintunde (2015) opined that teachers stress and good living is an established area for educational research over the years despite the fact that some researchers are of the perception that stress could be a motivating factor. (Stevie, Annemarie & Louise, 2021). As the teacher perform his duties, the experience of unpleasant emotions as a result of expectation and work load may lead to stress. Stress may also have a great effect on the teachers who are already advance in age, but have not retired from service. Stress can

come in the cause of work either internally or externally but the most important need is its management. Stress is any external event or any internal drive which threaten to upset the organism equilibrium. The word stress to Amalu and Achi (2020) was derived from Latin word “Stringer” which means to draw tight. There is no gain saying that stress is inevitable and unavoidable. It is a dynamic and complex concept which of growing concern to researchers, psychologists, educators, and even organizations.

Kaur, Kamari and Sharma (2013), describe stress as an adverse reaction that persons has to excessive pressure or other types of demands. This means that stress result when an individual’s adaptive capacity is unable to cope with demands. It is a fact that stress is neither good nor bad but depends on experience and management. It can be stimulant or energizer. (Alabi, Murtala & Lawal, 2012). According to Al-srouer and Al-Oweidi (2013) stress has direct effect on the body, but the level of stress people feel depends on factors such as how people perceive the stressful event, tolerance for stress and their personal beliefs about the resources they have to cope with the stressors.

According to Amalu and Achi (2020), there are different types of stress; Episodic Acute Stress, Is a situation where an individual experiences this type of stress it is very chaotic, out of control and always seen to be facing multiple stressful situations. People in this situation are always in a rush, always late, always taking too many projects and handling too many demands. And it is a fact that any individual who is prone to episodic acute stress, may find it so habitual to the extent that they resist changing their life styles until it leads them to experience severe physical symptoms.

Secondly, Chronic Stress, this type of stress is very dangerous. It is a type of stress that has unrelenting demands and pressure for seemingly interminable period of time. Chronic stress is the type that wears the individual out for a long period of time. It deals with both the emotional and the health of the individual leading to breakdown and even death.

Thirdly, Traumatic Stress, this is a severe stress reaction that results from a catastrophic event, such as natural disaster, sexual assault, life-threatening accident, or participation. After the initial shock and emotional fallout, many trauma victims gradually begin to recover. However, that will be the beginning of some persons psychological and physiological symptoms triggered by the trauma. And common symptoms of this types of stress are flashbacks or nightmares. But the solution to this is encouragement.

Finally, Acute Stress, this is the most common and recognizable form of stress. This is the type of stress which the individual knows exactly why he or she is stressed. For example, when the Vice Chancellor invites a staff over negligent of duty, he will be stress up. However, the human body relaxes when these stressful events cease and life gets back to normal because of the short-term effects.

Stress however can be caused by different factors such as interpersonal relationship which is considered as the various relationships between the lecturers and other people including his colleagues and these are bound to expose them to stress. Secondly, personality trait is a factor that also cause stress, for instance a lecturer with Type “A” personality is characterized by excessive competitive drive to accomplish more in less time, at times he tackles many activities at a time. He hardly or really wears himself away by work overload. Thirdly, poor work conditions is another cause of stress. The lecturers may be subjected to poor working conditions which includes poor ventilation, unhygienic sanitation facilities, poor lighting, excessive noise and dust, presence of toxic gasses and fumes, office adjacent to poultry. Some lecturers suffer uncountable denials in terms of office furnishing all this leads to stress. Fourthly, salaries and allowances. Non-payment of salaries for a couple of months. cutting of salaries and allowances of lecturers may lead to the inability of the lecturers to provide for their families.

Statement of the Problem

The academic environment of these days has drastically changed from just teaching and learning to more research activities. For this reason, Obidiegwu (2020), posited that Higher Education institutions have been strategically using research publication and teaching and learning as a yardstick for evaluation. As a result of the fact, this has led to increase of stress in the system. Thus, pressure been place on the workers on daily basis. It has become a great stress and interest to manage job stress. The rate of low job performance in Nigerian Universities might have been as a result of stress. This prompted Hall and Bowles (2016) and Obidiegwu (2020), acclaimed that the witnessing of the increase in the academic workplace pressure every day, management of job stress mostly academic related stress have remained a general concern. For the fact that stress is inevitable, stress management strategies have a perceived notoriety for been an important and broad subject of study.

Many have taken stress management for granted. But stress when not managed can generally make things and the body system go wrong. Many lecturers are facing the disease high blood pressure, ulcer, diabetes and even some have died as a result of stress. However, it depends on body system, because the stressor that affect an individual may not affect another. For this reason, Ingram, Maciejewski and Hand (2020), as cited in Brotohor (2021) posited that the situation that seems stressful to an individual may result to negative changes in their psychological lives, physical and mental wellbeing on the long term. As a matter of fact, when this issue of stress is been addressed, it will help lecturers to manage and cope with their stressors. The problem of this study therefore is job stress and management strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to assess causes of job stress and stress management strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Specifically, the objectives are to;

1. identify the causes of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka
2. identify the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka
3. assess job stress management strategies of lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What are the causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?
2. What are the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?
3. What are the stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been generated for the purpose of the study;

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating on causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating on symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean rating on coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Literature Review

Herzberg's Two-factor theory of motivation

Fredrick Herzberg, a psychologist developed the two-factor theory of motivation. The two factors are referred to as “motivators” and “hygiene”. He proposed that the presence of hygiene factors in the work place do not motivate but produces an acceptable working environment. Their absence did however cause job dissatisfaction. The presence of motivators causes enduring state of motivation in employees but their absence did not lead to dissatisfaction or demotivation.

However, Herzberg dual factor theory aimed at explaining the relationship between people’s motivation and job satisfaction. In relating this theory to the issue of job stress, there is no gainsaying that job stress is as a result of a number of factors as listed below; coworkers, uncooperative, job dissatisfaction, excessive workload and colleagues. (Sakwa, 2014). So many researchers in social sciences and other fields have used this theoretical Model in research relating to job stress (Adebiyi, 2013; Akinsolu & Ogbodinkpa, 2015; Obidiegwu, 2020)

Concept and Nature of Stress

Stress is a very important concept in medicine, physics as well as in the behavioural and management sciences. Stress is a popular work for both the educated and uneducated. It is often used to describe a wide range of feeling and situations. The word “stress” as employed in our everyday vocabulary can be said to be the abbreviated form of the word “distress”. Etymologically speaking, the term stress is derived from the Latin word “stringere”, meaning “to draw tight or hard”.

According to Obidiegwu (2020), he noted that the concept of stress was first coined in 1979 by Selye who view it as a personal encounter of non – specific feelings and symptoms of illness. To this note, Stranks (2015) posited that different personal, environmental, social and work-related factors is possibly used in defining the meaning of stress. As a result of this dimension of stress, Bhargava and Trivedi (2018), opine that stress is a choreographed state of events that affect all individual during a period of illness and not a psychological term. While Chan, Chen and Leung (2012) see stress as a psychological position of the mind which is as a result of demand posed on a person’s body. Also, Tapia, Pitt, Gray and Opresu (2018) as cited in Obidiegwu (2020), posited that stress experience is based on an individual’s subjective appraisal of a condition. He further said that this remains normal, inevitable and a result of been alive. Cole (2004) as cited in Sokpuwu and Ibrara (2021) sees stress as the physical and psychological reactions that happen to individuals as a result of their being unable to meet up with their demands posed on them.

Slyers (2011) as cited in Chukwu, Ezepue and Omede (2018) sees stress as a general response that the human body make to any demand on it, like physical worry, sociological, psychological which is as a result of not meeting with certain demands at the work place. Stress is also a process in which environmental forces or events threaten an organism well-being and the response of the individual. (Oboegbulem, 2007).

Causes of Stress

The potential causes or sources of stress are called stressors. Potential stressors may become actual stressors, thereby producing stress. The stress a worker experiences may be positive or negative depending on how the worker perceives and interprets the stressors. It also depends on individual differences.

According to Bhargava and Trivedi, (2018). The various factors that facilitate the development of chronic stress in workers can be put under three categories; personal stressors, organizational stressors and work – life linkages.

Symptoms of Stress

Workers differs in the extent to which they experience the consequences of stress, even when they are exposed to the same sources of stress. The consequences or symptoms of stress are of three main types; Physiological, Psychological and Behavioural. Each consequences have the power to affect well-being, performance and effectiveness at the individual, group and organizational levels. Some authors refer to the consequences as symptoms or manifestations of stress. (Peretomode, 2008).

Managing Academic Related Stress

Stress is a physiological and psychological response to occurrences that upset our personal balance when we are faced with a threat either to our emotional or physical safety equilibrium. According to Anovunga and Akpadago (2018) university occupation has its own demand, challenges, changes, and pressure on the employee. These demand employment. All the process involves in carrying out your duty can amount to the dreaded situation called “stress: due to challenges and changes in curriculum, meeting up with modern or sophisticated teaching aids, like ICT ways of learning and working hard for promotion, family pleasing, friend and personal desires. For this reason, Vermont and Steersman (2005) as cited in Anovunga and Akpadago (2018) sees stress is the perception of close rampancy between environmental demands (stressors) and individual capacity to fulfil these demands. Also, Campbell (2006) defined stress as the adverse reaction people have to go through excessive pressure or other types of demands placed on them. Stress comes in when an individual is challenged by a situation that he/she perceives as overwhelming and cannot cope with it. Stress response feels like heart pounding in the chest, muscles tensing up, breath coming fast and every sense of danger. In stressful situations, the heart rate and blood flow in the large muscles increase to enable us work harder. In case of injury the blood vessels under the skin construct to prevent blood loss. Also, body processes that are not essential to immediate survival is suppressed. It can go higher to affect the digestion and reproductive systems slowing down, growth hormones are switched off and the immune response is meant to protect and support us (Anovunga & Akpadago, 2018).

Context of Job Stress

According to Gupta and Bharathi (2017), as cited in Obidiegwu (2020), posited that job stress refers to the harmful physiological and psychological responses that occur when the requirement of the job does not match the capacity or need of the employee. As a matter of fact, we are currently living in a stressful generation, where an individual been occupied by so many jobs, and trying to meet up to expectation which leads to higher stress level.

Job stress to Gupta and Bharathi (2017) opined that job stress can be seen as the way an individual perceives and react to work environment that involves physiological and psychological threatening to the worker. This is simply the way an individual interprets his or her work environment whether will be able to cope with or not. Job stress can be escalated by

current changes in the work environment. (Scatter & Hassed, 2018). Job stress is as a result of state of the mind. For this stressor to an individual may not be to another. Jonker (2016) also posited that lack of proper job specification or role definition by employers may lead to stress because when the employee is caught up with role that is not his or hers, may become stressful. To Ismail (2015) he posited that work place stress comes up when worker's knowledge, abilities, attitude and skills cannot cope with demand or organizational pressures. Within the academic environment, job stress is escalated as a result of role ambiguity, conflict, work over load, lack of promotion, misunderstanding and communication. Managing this stressor have remain a challenge in the academic field because of the nature and structure of work involved.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. A descriptive survey design is used for this study because it is aimed at ascertaining and establishing the status quo, facts or pieces of information concerning the population, mostly for seeking individuals' opinion or perception in their natural setting. The target population for this study comprised 867 lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The sample comprises of a comprehensive data of the lecturers of three (3) faculties selected for the study.

The choice of these faculties is informed by the number of academic staff. The three faculties have the highest population of students among the eleven (11) faculties. In which case, it is expected that the lecturers in the three faculties are more likely to experience stress than those of the other less populated faculties. 100 items questionnaires were the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire titled "Job stress and management strategies questionnaire (JSMSQ)" was used. It has two parts A and B. Part A contain 4 items of demographic variables; Name of faculty, Sex, Rank and Job experience. Part B has three research questions which contains 83 items. The questionnaire items have the following response options; Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Research question 1: What are the causes of stress? (25 items), Research question 2: What are the symptoms of stress? (31 items), Research question 3: What are stress coping strategies? (27 items). To ensure reliability of the instrument, 35 copies of the questionnaire was administered to 35 lecturers in Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma in Edo State. The data collected was analysed using Cronbach Alpha. The reliability coefficient was used to determine the result. The test yielded a coefficient of 0.83.

The questionnaires was administered personally by the researcher to the 138 lecturers in Faculty of Education, 135 lecturers in faculty of Sciences and 81 lecturers in faculty of Social sciences, in Delta State University, Abraka, with the help of three trained assistants. The 97 questionnaire items were weighted as follows; Strongly Agree ---- 4 points, Agree ---- 3 points, Disagree ---- 2 point, Strongly disagree ---- 1. In cases where on on-the-spot completion and retrieval were not possible, the researcher and research assistants visited the faculties later times as agreed with the concerned respondents to collect the completed copies of the questionnaire. The rate of the returned stood at 354, out of 354 (100%).

To address the research questions, measures such as mean and standard deviation were employed. Additionally, to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05, an independent samples t-test was conducted. In answering the research question items In decision rule, any mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as agreed, while any mean score less than 2.5 is regarded as disagreed. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was utilized for performing the analysis.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?

Table 1: Mean analysis of the causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Change in your health	3.10	0.71	Agreed
2	Pressure at work	3.10	0.70	Agreed
3	Personal injury	3.09	0.79	Agreed
4	Always answering query in the office	3.04	0.78	Agreed
5	Work beyond normal working hours	3.03	0.59	Agreed
6	Low social support	3.01	0.72	Agreed
7	Divorce	2.98	0.79	Agreed
8	Work load at home and work place	2.97	0.66	Agreed
9	Separation of a partner	2.95	0.66	Agreed
10	Death of a partner	2.95	0.76	Agreed
11	Lack confidence and ability to handle problems at work	2.94	0.69	Agreed
12	Change in your financial state	2.90	0.98	Agreed
13	Pregnancy	2.74	0.84	Agreed
14	Loss of job	2.71	0.80	Agreed
15	Arguments with partner	2.64	0.74	Agreed
16	Jail sentence	2.39	0.88	Disagreed
17	Retirement	2.32	0.73	Disagreed
18	Reconciliation with a partner	2.29	0.73	Disagreed
19	Being under minded by the HOD	2.28	0.64	Disagreed
20	Marriage	2.25	0.71	Disagreed
21	Death of a friend	2.19	0.70	Disagreed
22	Trouble with in-laws	2.15	0.63	Disagreed
23	Salary is not paid regularly	2.15	0.77	Disagreed
24	Never receive overtime payment	2.10	0.67	Disagreed
25	There is tribal sentiment in m department	2.05	0.63	Disagreed
Average Mean		2.63	0.73	Agreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 1 shows the mean analysis of the causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. From the result, the mean ranged from 2.05 to 3.10, with an average mean of 2.63. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that 15 of the 25 items were agreed as causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka while 10 were disagreed.

Research Question 2: What are the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?

Table 2: Mean analysis of the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Hopelessness	3.32	0.81	Agreed
2	Poor concentration	3.17	0.95	Agreed
3	Worry	3.15	0.86	Agreed
4	Restlessness	3.07	0.89	Agreed
5	Angry	3.05	0.89	Agreed
6	Forgetfulness	3.00	0.67	Agreed
7	Sleep difficulties	2.99	0.86	Agreed
8	Aggressiveness	2.97	0.74	Agreed
9	Confusion	2.96	0.70	Agreed
10	Headache	2.93	0.80	Agreed
11	Depressed	2.90	0.86	Agreed
12	Loss of appetite	2.86	0.94	Agreed
13	Backache	2.79	0.73	Agreed
14	Fast breathing	2.65	0.79	Agreed
15	Ulcer	2.56	0.87	Agreed

16	Internal heat	2.49	0.68	Disagreed
17	Alcohol or drug abuse	2.49	0.80	Disagreed
18	Infertility	2.48	0.79	Disagreed
19	Pessimistic	2.47	0.89	Disagreed
20	Isolated	2.42	0.79	Disagreed
21	Constipation	2.40	0.86	Disagreed
22	Emotional outbursts	2.37	0.77	Disagreed
23	Tensed	2.32	0.84	Disagreed
24	Anxious	2.31	0.67	Disagreed
25	Fatigue	2.29	0.77	Disagreed
26	Sweaty palms	2.27	0.71	Disagreed
27	Trembling	2.25	0.70	Disagreed
28	Rashes	2.23	0.80	Disagreed
29	Irritability	2.19	0.63	Disagreed
30	Overwhelmed	2.09	1.17	Disagreed
31	Rashes	1.96	0.68	Disagreed
Average Mean		2.63	0.80	Agreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 2 shows the mean analysis of the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. From the result, the mean ranged from 1.96 to 3.32, with an average mean of 2.63. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that 15 of the 31 items were agreed as symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka while 16 were disagreed.

Research Question 3: What are the stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka?

Table 3: Mean analysis of the stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD	Remark
1	Adequate sleeping	3.49	0.65	Agreed
2	Forgiving others	3.43	0.74	Agreed
3	Being realistic	3.38	0.77	Agreed
4	Division of labour	3.36	0.74	Agreed
5	Saying no to unreasonable demands	3.30	0.69	Agreed
6	Positive thinking	3.29	0.68	Agreed
7	Deliberately avoiding stressful situations	3.28	0.54	Agreed
8	Go for medical checks often	3.28	0.69	Agreed
9	Sharing feelings with trusted friends	3.28	0.79	Agreed
10	Eating a healthy diet	3.27	0.69	Agreed
11	Self-Control	3.24	0.64	Agreed
12	Providing workers with job security	3.22	0.76	Agreed
13	Forgiving yourself	3.22	0.75	Agreed
14	Creating time for leisure activities	3.21	0.70	Agreed
15	Proper time management	3.19	0.61	Agreed
16	Keeping a sense of humour	3.18	0.71	Agreed
17	Relying on supportive colleagues	3.15	0.58	Agreed
18	Doing the things, you like and enjoy doing	3.14	0.72	Agreed
19	Going for clinical counselling	3.12	0.53	Agreed
20	Taking vital medications	3.08	0.54	Agreed
21	Accept help with ease when offered	3.07	0.65	Agreed
22	Expressing feelings instead of bottling them up	3.03	0.75	Agreed
23	Getting help from a mentor	2.89	0.62	Agreed
24	Non-competitive physical exercise	2.77	0.62	Agreed
25	Optimistic	2.62	0.86	Agreed
26	Relaxing from routine work	2.36	0.83	Disagreed

27	Reward	2.20	0.72	Disagreed
Average Mean		3.11	0.69	Agreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Table 3 shows the mean analysis of the stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. From the result, the mean ranged from 2.20 to 3.49, with an average mean of 3.11. The criterion mean used is 2.50, which means that 25 of the 27 items were agreed as stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka while 2 were disagreed.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

Table 4: t-test comparison of the difference in the mean rating of causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	P	Remark
Male	189	2.67	0.30				
Female	165	2.64	0.31	352	0.90	0.37	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 4 shows the result of an independent t-test, which was used to compare the comparison of the difference in the mean rating of causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The result shows that $t(352) = 0.90$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore agreed, which means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Table 5: t-test comparison of the difference in mean ratings of the symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	P	Remark
Male	189	2.64	0.38				
Female	165	2.61	0.34	352	0.91	0.36	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 5 shows the result of an independent t-test, which was used to compare the comparison of the difference in the mean rating of symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The result shows that $t(352) = 0.91$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore agreed, which means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Table 6: t-test comparison of the difference in mean ratings of the coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	T	P	Remark
Male	189	3.13	0.31				
Female	165	3.09	0.33	352	1.12	0.26	Not Significant

$\alpha = 0.05$

Table 7 shows the result of an independent t-test, which was used to compare the comparison of the difference in the coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The result shows that $t(352) = 1.12$, $p > 0.05$ level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore accepted, which means that there is no significant difference in the coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding revealed that the causes of job stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka include change in your health pressure at work, personal injury, always answering query in the office, work beyond normal working hours, low social support, divorce, work load at home and work place. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of causes of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The findings of this study have implications for the management of stress among lecturers. Universities need to provide lecturers with support to help them cope with the demands of their job. For instance, a study by Obi and Oghounu (2019) found that the most common causes of stress among lecturers in Delta State, Nigeria were work overload, poor working conditions, interpersonal conflict, financial pressure and lack of support.

The second finding showed that the symptoms of stress among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka include hopelessness, poor concentration, worry, restlessness, angry, forgetfulness, sleep difficulties, aggressiveness and confusion. A corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of symptoms of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The findings of this study have implications for the identification and management of stress among lecturers. Universities need to be aware of the common symptoms of job stress so that they can identify lecturers who may be struggling. Universities should also provide support and resources to help lecturers cope with stress.

The third finding revealed that the stress coping strategies among lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka include adequate sleeping, forgiving others, being realistic, division of labour, saying no to unreasonable demands, positive thinking, deliberately avoiding stressful situations, go for medical checks often, sharing feelings with trusted friends, eating a healthy diet, self-control, providing workers with job security and forgiving yourself. A corresponding hypothesis showed that there is no significant difference in the coping strategies of job stress between Male and Female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka. The findings of this study have implications for the management of stress among lecturers. Universities need to be aware of the common coping strategies that lecturers use so that they can provide support and resources to help them cope effectively. A study by Babatope (2015) found that the most common stress coping strategies among lecturers in southern Nigeria were social support, relaxation techniques, exercise, time management, problem-solving, humour, avoiding negative thinking and self-care.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that lecturers experience a variety of stressors, including work overload, poor working conditions, interpersonal conflict, financial pressure and lack of support. These stressors can lead to a variety of symptoms, including physical symptoms such as headache, fatigue, muscle tension, and sleep problems; emotional symptoms such as anxiety, depression, anger, and irritability; cognitive symptoms such as difficulty concentrating, forgetfulness, and decision-making problems; and behavioural symptoms such as increased smoking, drinking, and caffeine consumption; changes in eating habits; and withdrawal from social activities. Lecturers use a variety of coping strategies to

deal with stress, including social support, relaxation techniques, exercise, time management, problem-solving, humour, avoiding negative thinking and self-care. There is no significant difference in the causes, symptoms, coping strategies, and implications of job stress between male and female lecturers in Delta State University, Abraka.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Management should address the common stressors that lecturers face, such as work overload, poor working conditions, and financial pressure.
2. Management should provide lecturers with support to help them cope with stress, such as counselling, stress management workshops, and flexible work arrangements.
3. Lecturers should develop healthy coping strategies for dealing with stress, such as exercise, relaxation techniques, and social support.

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